

Automating 5G network slice management for industrial applications

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ABSTRACT

The transition to Industry 4.0 introduces new use cases with unique communication requirements, demanding wireless technologies capable of dynamically adjusting their performance to meet various demands. Leveraging network slicing, 5G technology offers the flexibility to support such use cases. However, the usage and deployment of network slices in networks are complex tasks. To increase the adoption of 5G, there is a need for mechanisms that automate the deployment and management of network slices. This paper introduces a design for a network slice manager capable of such mechanisms in 5G networks. This design adheres to related standards, facilitating interoperability with other software, while also considering the capabilities and limitations of the technology. The proposed design can provision custom slices tailored to meet the unique requirements of verticals, offering communication performance across the spectrum of the three primary 5G services (eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC/mIoT). To access the proposed design, a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) prototype was developed and evaluated. The evaluation results demonstrate the flexibility of the proposed solution for deploying slices adjusted to the vertical use cases. Additionally, the slices generated by the PoC maintain a high TRL (Technology Readiness Level) equivalent to that of the commercial-graded network used.

1. Introduction

The industry is expected to experience the Fourth Industrial Revolution named Industry 4.0 (I4.0). This revolution is expected to impact the entire production line by increasing the connectivity between equipment through the application of the Internet of Things (IoT) directly in industrial processes, which was named Industrial IoT (IIoT). Consequently, this can lead to substantial cost reduction, heightened production efficiency, improved worker safety, higher customization of products, and enhanced material quality. Since 5G is one of the technologies capable of providing the necessary connectivity for the revolution, the industry has become actively engaged in advancing and standardizing this technology. This has led to the integration of old and new technologies such as TSN (Time Sensitive Networking) [1] and 5G-NPN (5G Non-Public Network) [2], and the development of novel use cases based on diverse technologies within 5G, such as Edge computing [3] and Sidelink [4].

Industries must optimize all equipment and processes in their production to remain competitive and maximize resource usage. In this optimization journey, 5G will become one of the key assets, with network slicing emerging as a crucial mechanism. Network slicing enables network customization to accommodate various communications needs, thereby optimizing network resource usage.

Therefore, for wide adoption of 5G, it is crucial to deploy network slices aligned with the communication requirements, enforcing a slice tailored to the specific needs of the use case, thereby optimizing resource usage. However, configuring 5G is complex and requires expertise. Manual configuration of network slices is time-consuming and error-prone. Therefore, an automation mechanism capable of converting high-level requirements into low-level configurations is necessary.

There are numerous works in the literature that enable various QoS configurations and other 5G features to optimize resource usage, such as those presented in [5–9], and [10]. The extensive research on resource optimization using network slices highlights the importance of optimizing network slice resource usage. Additionally, authors in [10] conclude that resource optimization is extremely important for the deployment of the different use cases evaluated.

Despite the significant importance of network slicing, previous work highlighted in [11] revealed the absence of a widely available mechanism for deploying and managing network slices in 5G networks. With no existing mechanism or network function to provide and manage 5G slices, the focus shifted towards developing a network slice manager, as presented in this paper.

The work examined industry requirements for leveraging 5G technology in their processes, highlighting the crucial role of network

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slicing in providing mechanisms for verticals to control communication performance according to their requirements. Subsequent efforts focused on analyzing and understanding existing mechanisms within the 5G network capable of adapting network performance to meet industrial requirements.

The analysis started with [11], which introduced the Quality of Service (QoS) model and assessed the available Release 15 (R15) QoS configurations, emphasizing their predominant impact on throughput. This initial investigation prompted a deeper examination of 5G features and technologies. [12] analyzed standardized features of Release 17 (R17) 5G Radio Access Network (RAN), while [13] focused on 5G features tailored to emulate performance similar to a massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) slice. Building upon these insights, [14] mapped the 5G features to industrial use cases and network slice attributes. The resulting mapping was assessed to demonstrate its effectiveness in optimizing network performance according to requirements, with limitations imposed by available resources and network capabilities. This comprehensive study provided the foundational knowledge essential for automating network slice deployment.

The analysis presented in previous work [11–14] was important for understanding the functioning of the 5G network. This knowledge is essential for designing and developing an automated system that deploys and manages network slices. Since it is not possible to design and develop a slice manager solution without a complete understanding of the 5G network, it was necessary to first understand the operational details and how they can be controlled to effectively manage network slices.

The accumulated knowledge is then leveraged in this paper to design the network slice manager presented in this document. This proposed solution enables the programmatic reconfiguration of a 5G network to ensure it supports the slices demanded by industrial users while adhering to slice manager standards. To achieve this, the network slice manager maps network slice requirements to low-level network configurations and provides these configurations to a Digital Twin (DT). The DT then enforces the necessary configurations on the network to ensure the required slice is supported. The low-level configurations used include the QoS mechanism, 5G features, and other technologies assessed in previous work.

The design was implemented in a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) prototype, developed specifically to configure the 5GAIner network [15]. This document assesses the capabilities of the proposed solution, aiming to demonstrate its effectiveness. The main contributions of the developed solution are outlined below:

- (1) The network slice manager generates slices tailored to one of the three primary 5G services [eMBB (enhanced Mobile Broadband), prioritizing throughput and spectral efficiency, URLLC (Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication), focusing on low latency and high reliability, and mMTC/mIoT (massive Internet of Things), aiming for low device energy consumption and high connection density] based on provided network Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- (2) Within each service type, the network slice manager offers complete customization of slice construction to meet specific requirements.
- (3) The slices configured by the network slice manager preserve the network Technology Readiness Level (TRL), being the produced slices representative of a commercial-graded solution.
- (4) The slice manager provides dynamic slicing enabling the adaptation of the slice performance in real time without communication disruption.

The remaining sections of the document are as follows: Section 2 briefly analyses related work. Section 3 provides a summarized list of requirements for a slice manager and compares the proposed solution with existing solutions. Section 4 introduces the standards involved

in 5G network slice automation and describes the proposed design for a network slice manager. Section 5 presents 5GAIner and provides an overview of the developed PoC, including a brief discussion of each component of the solution. Section 6 introduces the parameters of three network slices used to evaluate the solution and describes how the performance assessment was executed. Section 7 presents and discusses obtained results. Section 8 has the final discussion and conclusions of the document.

2. Related work

In light of the potentially transformative impact of 5G technology, the industry has actively engaged in its development, leading to the establishment of various industrial organizations such as 5G-ACIA,¹ 6G-IA,² and 5G-DNA.³ These organizations play key roles in 5G technology standardization, promotion, and evaluation.

Through their interactions with the technology, industrial organizations have developed and promoted numerous use cases that leverage the capabilities of 5G networks. Examples of these use cases can be found in [3,4,16], and [17].

Several projects leverage numerous 5G testbeds, such as [18–22], and [15], as well as those developed by European projects like 5G-EVE,⁴ 5G-VINNI,⁵ and 5GENESIS.⁶ These testbeds are used for developing, testing, and validating numerous industrial use cases. In different research projects, among these projects are:

- 5GASP,⁷ which, while capable of providing limited configurability of eMBB slices on the 5G network, primarily relies on default network configurations.
- 5G-ERA,⁸ allowing the selection of pre-configured network profiles tailored to the specific requirements of the use case.
- Smart5Grid,⁹ which implements a slice manager for logical isolation between slices in the core. In the RAN, slice management involves direct allocation of physical resources, with limited configuration options for network features affecting prioritization and resource sharing.
- 5GMediaHUB¹⁰ uses slices to manage services and Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), although specific details regarding their 5G configurations are not publicly available;
- Imagine-B5G,¹¹ divided into four facilities, each employing specific mechanisms for slice deployment and management. The French facility allocates RAN physical resources into each slice. The Norwegian Facility configures different User Plane Functions (UPF) and control plane functions for each slice, with some QoS configurability in the Policy Control Function (PCF). Domain A of the Portuguese facility uses the network slice manager outlined in this document, while Domain B offers eMBB and URLLC slices with limited QoS configurations. The Spanish facility allows one UPF per slice and offers limited QoS configuration options.

Besides the work on projects related to managing network slices in the 5G network, there is also some research. In [23], the authors analyzed the usage of Network Function Virtualization (NFVs) to support network slices, demonstrating that the NFV platform is robust for this

¹ <https://5g-acia.org/>, (April 2024).

² <https://6g-ia.eu/>, (April 2024).

³ https://www.5gdna.org/?_l=en&_l=en, (April 2024).

⁴ <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>, (March 2023).

⁵ <https://www.5g-vinni.eu/>, (March 2023).

⁶ <https://5genesis.eu/>, (March 2023).

⁷ <https://www.5gasp.eu/>, (December 2023).

⁸ <https://5g-era.eu/>, (December 2023).

⁹ <https://smart5grid.eu/>, (December 2023).

¹⁰ <https://www.5gmediahub.eu/>, (December 2023).

¹¹ <https://imagineb5g.eu/>, (December 2023).

purpose. In [24], the authors developed a solution to manage and orchestrate network slices in an OpenAirInterface 4G network. Similarly, the authors in [25] devised solutions for Non-3GPP networks, which can adjust network slice performance and deploy multiple network slices in their testbed.

While surveying the current state of the art, we identified already extensive work around network slices, such as [5–8], and [9], that do not explicitly focus on the development of the slice management model already provide some differentiated Quality of Service. Other articles, such as [26,27], and [28], are focused on the algorithms and resource allocation in network slicing. Some articles, like [29,30], and [31], research on the coexistence between eMBB and URLLC slices. Other articles focus on orchestrating network slices, such as [32,33], and [34]. However, no research was found addressing the development of a network slice manager capable of translating Network Slice Descriptor (NSD) parameters into low-level 5G configurations while ensuring the realistic performance aligns with the specified NSD parameters.

Since there is a lack of research on the management level of slices, and considering the importance of a network slice manager capable of adjusting the 5G network to provide a custom network slice that ensures required use case performance while fulfilling the demanded SLAs, the following section analyzes the requirements that a network slice manager should fulfill and discusses the capabilities of the existing slice managers.

3. Slice manager requirements

Industrial organizations proposed many use cases with completely distinct requirements, demanding extreme network flexibility to accommodate them. However, existing network slice managers supported by projects and research have limitations in configuration. They cannot adjust the 5G network to ensure the required performance for each use case. The proposed use cases necessitate a more flexible network slice manager capable of configuring the 5G network to support the required network slice, ensuring the necessary performance for each use case. Over the past few years, several open-source and proprietary solutions have been researched and developed.

To characterize the network slice manager solutions, the standard documentation has been reviewed to define the requirements list that a network slice manager needs to fulfill. The main standard documents used to extract the requirements are [35–37]. A large number of requirements are defined in these documents. Several requirements have been summarized and aggregated from this list to produce the most important network slice manager requirements identified by the authors. The resulting list of requirements is as follows:

- E2E (End-to-End) Slice Support: The solution enables authorized users to manage the complete slice by interacting with the necessary slice and slice subnet instances in the RAN, CN, and TN, ensuring the required slice capacities across the communication link.
- Manage Slice Lifecycle: The solution supports the different stages of the slice lifecycle, including activation, deactivation, modification, and termination.
- Network Slice Mapping: The solution uses slice requirements provided in a GST template, service profile, or slice profile to decide whether to use an existing or create a new network slice. It generates slice configurations necessary for the network to meet performance requirements and adjust slice resource access according to slice priorities.
- Network Configuration: The solution configures NF (Network Function) instances (New Generation-RAN [NG-RAN] functions, TN functions, and 5G core functions [User and Control Plane 5G functions]), applying the necessary configurations provided by the mapping, thus ensuring the support of the required slice on the network.

- Policy and QoS Management for SLA Enforcement: The solution can adjust communication rules (e.g., PCC [Policy and Charging Control] rule) and QoS configurations to enforce the required slice Service Level Agreements (SLAs).
- Dynamic Slicing: The solution can seamlessly adjust QoS configurations and communication rules, changing slice communication performance without interfering with end device communications.
- Custom Slices: The solution supports the deployment of any slice on the available network, allowing for the deployment of custom slices tailored to specific user requirements.
- Network Slice Monitoring: The solution can monitor resources used by the provided network slices and report KPIs to authorized consumers.
- Location-based Slicing: The solution enforces the required slice only in the specified coverage area, configuring the NFs responsible for that designated area. UEs accessing areas outside the coverage have no service or use a default eMBB slice.
- Performance Assurance: The solution collects and analyzes relevant data and KPIs, using thresholds to verify the fulfillment of slice requirements for charging policies and performance adjustment.
- Manage Multiple Slices: The solution possesses management capabilities for deploying and managing multiple independent slices. It can manage different slices in various stages of the slice lifecycle and differentiate communication among different slices.
- Monitor Network Resources: The solution can monitor available and used network resources.
- Evaluate Slice Feasibility: In the case of multi-slicing, the solution should verify the feasibility of deploying a new slice without impacting existing slices, ensuring the existence of adequate available network resources.
- Generic Network Support: The solution can support any standardized network function from any network provider.

Beyond the above-compiled list of requirements, exists numerous other crucial requirements for a complete network slice manager solution, such as support for Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), network services, and multiple domains. These requirements were omitted from the list for two reasons: firstly, the document centers on network slice provision in a 5G network, and secondly, the provided solution can be integrated with OSM and OpenSlice, which already fulfill most of the omitted requirements.

While searching for tools capable of managing 5G networks the following were found: Openslice,¹² OPEN BATON,¹³ Open Source MANO (OSM),¹⁴ SliMANO [38], Nokia Network as Code (NaC),¹⁵ Open Air Interface (OAI) Operation and Maintenance (OAM),¹⁶ and 5Growth-VS [39]. But while reading the tools documentation became clear that: Openslice is a vertical portal; OPEN BATON and OSM are network service managers and orchestrators, not addressing any management or orchestration of network slices, so these tools are not further discussed. SliMANO is a proposed framework that has not been developed. Nokia NaC and 5Growth-VS are network slice orchestrators, which use a network slice manager to interact with the network. OAI OAM operates and maintains the 5G infrastructure, not specifically focused on deploying and managing network slices.

In Table 1, the functionalities of tools interacting with the 5G network are summarized, compared to the Proposed Solution. In the

¹² <https://openslice.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (December 2023).

¹³ <https://openbaton.github.io/features.html> (December 2023).

¹⁴ <https://osm.etsi.org/> (December 2023).

¹⁵ <https://www.nokia.com/networks/network-as-code/> (December 2023).

¹⁶ <https://openairinterface.org/projects/oam-project-group/> (December 2023).

Table 1
Network slice managers.

Automation tool	SliMANO	Nokia NaC	OAI OAM	5Growth-VS	Proposed solution
Functionality					
E2E slice support	✓	✓		✓	✓
Manage slice lifecycle	✓	✓		✓	✓
Network slice mapping			✓	✓	✓
Network configuration		✓		✓	✓
Policy and QoS management for SLA Enforcement		✓		✓	✓
Dynamic slicing					✓
Custom slices					✓
Network slice monitoring	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Location-based slicing					✓
Performance assurance					✓
Manage multiple slices		✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitor network resources					✓
Evaluate slice feasibility					✓
Generic network support					✓

table, a “✓” denotes that the tool supports the functionality, while blank entries indicate functionalities not mentioned in the tool’s documentation.

SliMANO, Nokia Nac, and 5Growth-VS primarily focus on orchestration and high-level management aspects of 5G, lacking comprehensive management capabilities and detailed insights into the intricacies of the 5G network. As a result, many important management-level functionalities are left unaddressed, leading to numerous empty cells in the table. Among the reviewed tools, only OAI OAM offers capabilities to adjust the low-level configuration of a 5G network. However, it lacks integration with high-level management and orchestration of network slices, further highlighting the gap in comprehensive 5G network management solutions.

Given the significant absence of solutions capable of managing 5G networks to provide slices tailored to end-user requirements, this document proposes the design of a network slice manager. This manager aims to bridge the gap between low-level 5G network configurations and high-level Network Service Descriptor (NSD) parameters.

Based on this design, a PoC was developed, more focused on vertical use cases. The objective is to provide E2E slices that meet user requirements while considering the realistic impact of each configuration. The developed network slice manager can configure a commercial Standalone (SA) 5G network with multiple network slices, adjusting communication performance based on user requirements outlined in a slice or service profile.

4. Standards and slice manager design

Compliance with existing standards was essential to develop a network slice manager capable of configuring the 5G network to support desired network slices. Section 4.1 introduces the 3GPP standards considered in the design and development of the slice manager. Section 4.2 presents the overall design of the slice manager.

4.1. Network slice automation standards

Standardization bodies such as 3GPP and .541 IETF have established various standard definitions for network slice managers. Therefore, when developing any slice manager, it is crucial to adhere to these standards to facilitate interoperability and interaction with other software. The standards considered in the design are the following:

- 3GPP TS 28.531 [40]: This document outlines the essential Network Functions for a standardized network slice manager, including Communication Service Management Function (CSMF), Network Slice Management Function (NSMF), and Network Slice Subnet Management Function (NSSMF) of the different segments of the network Core Network (CN), Transport Network (TN), and RAN.

Fig. 1. Proposed network slice manager design.

- 3GPP TR 28.824 [41]: It identifies the Tele Management Forum standards (TMFs) required for the slice manager. It specifies that CSMF should adhere to TMF622_ProductOrder,¹⁷ and NSMF should support TMF641_ServiceOrder.¹⁸
- 3GPP TS 28.541 [42]: This document delineates the profiles associated with network slices, including ServiceProfile, TOP-SliceSubnetProfile, CNSliceSubnetProfile, RANsliceSubnetProfile, NsacInfoSnsai, and the NSACFFunction.
- 3GPP TS 28.530 [35]: It presents the Network Slice Management Lifecycle.

4.2. Network slice manager design

The proposed network slice manager design is shown in Fig. 1, using the knowledge gathered from previous analyses and considering the standards. This design has three main components: the Slice Manager, the Mapping, and the Digital Twin.

4.2.1. Slice manager

Taking into account what 3GPP defines for the Slice Manager presented in Section 4.1. In the design of the slice manager, it is considered the maximum number of standards possible to increase interoperability with other software. Therefore, the design comprises the distinct network functions identified in the standards, containing the CSMF, NSMF, NSSMF-CN, NSSMF-TN, NSSMF-RAN, and Network Slice Admission Control Function (NSACF). Within the CSMF and NSMF, the endpoints identified in the TMFs should be included. Additionally, the

¹⁷ https://github.com/tmforum-apis/TMF622_ProductOrder/tree/master, (December 2023).

¹⁸ https://github.com/tmforum-apis/TMF641_ServiceOrder/tree/master, (December 2023).

Fig. 2. Components of proposed network slice manager.

network slices within each network function are identified with the following profiles: ServiceProfile in CSMF, TOPSliceSubnetProfile in NSMF, CNSliceSubnetProfile in NSSMF-CN, RANsliceSubnetProfile in NSSMF-RAN, and a list composed of NsacInfoSnsai in NSACF.

The NSACF is responsible for anything related to the association of User Equipments (UEs) with the network slices, such as linking UEs to slices and limiting the number of UEs per slice.

The NSSMF-TN is currently being standardized by IETF, as described in [43]. However, since this work primarily focuses on optimizing 5G technology and the transport network uses technologies such as Software-defined networking (SDN), where extensive development has already been done on NSSMF-TN, as evidenced by the work presented in [44]. Therefore, this document will no longer discuss NSSMF-TN, remaining here solely for the completion of the design.

Fig. 2 presents the different components expected in a final version of a network Slice Manager. This image is based on the requirements discussed in Section 3. At its core, the slice Manager must provide multiple network slices and convert slice parameters into network configurations. This requires support for managing multiple slices, E2E slice support, and network slice mapping to convert slice requirements into network configurations. A simple implementation can offer a set of preconfigured network slices.

Dynamic Slicing capability can enhance this base component, allowing for more adaptable network slices. Dynamic slicing can be used for performance assurance or to adjust slice performance as required by a vertical application, potentially due to traffic changes. The effective function of these core components necessitates network resource monitoring and the capacity to evaluate slice feasibility.

To fully manage the slice lifecycle, the slice manager needs network slice monitoring for slice supervision. This enables it to generate necessary reports when slice performance is not assured. With supervision and reporting capabilities, the slice manager can use dynamic slicing to adjust and assure slice performance.

4.2.2. Mapping

As mentioned earlier, the simplest implementation of slice mapping involves selecting a pre-configured slice. However, the network slice mapping can be enhanced with the capability to provide slice customization, as illustrated in Fig. 2. This customization is enabled by location-based slicing and adjustment to Policy and QoS management enforcing the required SLAs.

For comprehensive slice customization, the Mapping should consist of three separate components: RAN Mapping, a part of NSSMF-RAN; CN Mapping, a part of NSSMF-CN; and UE Mapping, a component of

NSACF. The CN and RAN mappings handle the conversion between Slice subnet profiles and standard 5G network functionalities, involving QoS configurations and other 5G features. The UE mapping converts end device parameters to network functionalities, manages the association between UE and slice, and extracts slice parameters necessary for UE configuration. The different mapping components must interact to ensure that the configurations provided to the DT will properly configure the E2E slices.

4.2.3. Digital twin

The Digital Twin (DT) is a digital replica of the 5G network, encompassing a digital copy of the entire 5G infrastructure. It includes the 5G RAN, TN, and the 5G Core Twin, each containing comprehensive information about its corresponding component. The DT tracks network status, alarms, resources, and configurations and monitors devices and network configurations. Consequently, the DT will know available, allocated, and used resources, the status of different network components, and details of connected UEs, including used slices, communication performance, and resource consumption.

All these capabilities provide additional functionalities to the DT. However, in this design, the primary purpose of the DT is to standardize interaction with the 5G network. This enables the Slice Manager to access standard APIs and use standard configurations and monitoring capabilities, making the Slice Manager generic enough to support any network.

Even though the 5G network functions are standardized, their implementation, limitations, and interactions may vary across network implementations. The DT grants the slice manager access to all network capabilities while maintaining its generic nature to support Network Functions from any provider. This ensures that the slice manager can effectively manage network slices, regardless of potential differences in network implementations.

One example of the importance of DT is translating standard QoS configurations and 5G features to the configurations available in the network. Since each implementation of a 5G network can have different names and slightly different implementations for each of the 5G features, the DT needs to make a secondary mapping between the standard and actual functionalities of the network implementation.

5. Developed network slice manager prototype

To validate the proposed design for a network slice manager, a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) has been developed based on the proposed design. This was mainly developed to interact and configure a

Fig. 3. Slice manager PoC final integration to Imagine-B5G Portuguese facility.

commercial-graded SA 5G network, ensuring it can support custom network slices and dynamic slicing. This section provides an overview of the developed network slice manager PoC.

The developed solution adheres to the design presented in Section 4.2, with slight adaptations made for various reasons. These include enhanced configurability for the user, improved security, and smoother interaction between functions. The current capabilities and adaptations of the developed PoC are outlined in the following subsections.

The current PoC accepts REST requests to configure the 5G network, allowing it to work with Postman¹⁹ and any software capable of sending REST commands. The PoC can be converted into a container for easy deployment, management, and replication. The final integration of the slice manager PoC into the Imagine-B5G Portuguese facility is represented in Fig. 3, as described in [45].

It is essential to note that this software represents an initial version developed for PoC demonstrations of proposed functionalities. Future iterations will integrate enhancements and additional features. The current version of the software exhibits expected design limitations and areas marked for improvement, partly due to constraints in interacting with the 5G network used. One of the anticipated improvements will involve the DT by modifying its interaction with the 5G network and enhancing it with more functionalities.

5.1. Slice manager

The developed solution includes all standard network functions. The external endpoints of CSMF and NSMF, as identified in the TMFs, are currently limited to create, update, delete, and get. These endpoints are open as a REST request, enabling the end user to interact with the PoC to implement and configure the necessary network slices.

Considering the requirements imposed on a Slice Manager discussed in Section 3, Fig. 4 presents the components implemented in the PoC. In blue and orange, the component is already implemented and presented in this document; in yellow, the component is implemented but not presented here; and in gray, the component is not implemented.

The image illustrates that the current PoC already supports the base components of a slice manager: managing multiple slices, supporting E2E slices, mapping network slices to network configurations, and enabling dynamic slicing. It also includes the essential capabilities of network resource monitoring and slice feasibility evaluation, which are crucial for the operation of the other components. As expected, the PoC supports only part of the slice lifecycle management, lacking

supervision and reporting. As a result, dynamic slicing can only be triggered by external requests.

In addition to the profiles identified for different functions, the solution incorporates additional variables aimed at providing enhanced control of network slices to end-users or facilitating slice management between functions. For example, the “DNN” (Data Network Name) and “Name” parameters in CSMF and NSMF serve the former purpose. Meanwhile, the “fiveQI” parameter was introduced in NSMF functions to facilitate the interconnection of RAN and CN mapping, ensuring end-to-end slice control and interoperability.

The DNN parameter within CSMF and NSMF empowers end-users by granting them complete control over the slice. This control involves defining the SNSSAI (Single-Network Slice Selection Assistance Information) [SST (Slice/Service Type) + SD (Slice Differentiator)] and the DNN, which leads to a more isolated network slice for the end user. Assigning unique DNN and SNSSAI ensures that the slice remains exclusive to the user, creating unique network configurations tailored to the required slice.

The “Name” parameter enables dynamic slicing by the network slice manager. This parameter specifies the slices used in dynamic slicing, and these slices share user profiles, which reduces isolation between them. However, sharing user profiles across slices with different purposes introduces security vulnerabilities, prompting the inclusion of this parameter.

Dynamic slicing relies on specific network functionalities that may not be present in other 5G network implementations. In this case, during the dynamic slice transition, in UPF, old slice rules are removed from the user profile while new slice rules are added, and in UDM, the UEs are associated with the new slice.

Due to the absence of certain network functions in the utilized network and the intricate nature of the 5G network, not all profile parameters were thoroughly explored in this initial version of the software. The parameters currently employed by the CSMF and NSMF in the slice creation are outlined in Table 2, along with their expected values.

The expected values vary depending on standard requirements, network configurations, or implementation decisions. To differentiate between restrictions stemming from network configuration (⊗) and implementation decisions (✳), symbols are placed before the restriction.

In [40], concrete values for N6protection were not specifically defined. Therefore, it was utilized to establish UPF Rules, which currently support the PCC (Policy and Charging Control) rules and their corresponding filters. The filter parameters are described in Appendix A.1.

The current software aligns with the instances depicted in Fig. 5 reflecting the Network Slice Life Cycle Management defined in [35]. Thus, the software is currently configured to support various stages of the Network Slice Lifecycle, including Creation, Activation, Modification, Deactivation, and Termination.

The slice manager also includes a simplified version of the NSACF with the UE mapping, which facilitates the linkage between UEs and slices while extracting essential values from the slice profiles required for the UE configurations within the 5G network. This NSACF contains a simplified list of parameters compared to the ones defined in the standard; the supported parameters can be seen in Appendix A.2.

5.2. Mapping

The mapping of slice parameters to network configurations is a pivotal aspect of the developed solution addressed here. All components of this mapping process have been implemented, enabling the support for custom slice through location-based slicing and policy and QoS management for SLA enforcement and ultimately converting everything into network configurations. As mentioned earlier, the Mapping is segmented into three parts: RAN mapping, CN mapping, and UE mapping. The mapping involves diverse network configurations, a concise impact description for each configuration is provided in Appendix A.3.

¹⁹ <https://www.postman.com/>, (May 2024).

Fig. 4. PoC implemented components.

Table 2
Supported profile parameters.

Parameter name	Expected value
Slice identification	str (any value @not allowed [;=])
Name	str (any value @not allowed [;=])
Administrative state	str (LOCKED - UNLOCKED - SHUTTINGDOWN)
Operational state	str (ENABLED - DISABLED)
Coverage area	list of strings with names of selected areas
SST (Slice/Service Type)	int (0-255)
SD (Slice Descriptor)	str @with six numbers
DNN	*str of DNN used
Priority label	int *(0-100)
UE mobility level	str (stationary - nomadic - restricted_mobility - fully_mobility)
Reliability	float (0-100)
Uplink max packet size	int @bytes
Downlink latency	int milliseconds
Uplink latency	int milliseconds
Delay tolerance	str (SUPPORTED - NOT_SUPPORTED)
Downlink deterministic communication	str (SUPPORTED - NOT_SUPPORTED)
Downlink deterministic periodicity	int *milliseconds
Uplink deterministic communication	str (SUPPORTED - NOT_SUPPORTED)
Uplink deterministic periodicity	int *milliseconds
Downlink guaranteed throughput per UE	int *kbit/s
Uplink guaranteed throughput per UE	int *kbit/s
Downlink maximum throughput per UE	int *kbit/s
Uplink maximum throughput per UE	int *kbit/s
Downlink guaranteed throughput per slice	int *kbit/s
Uplink guaranteed throughput per slice	int *kbit/s
Downlink maximum throughput per slice	int *kbit/s
Uplink maximum throughput per slice	int *kbit/s
Terminal density	int @UEs per antenna
Maximum number of PDU (Protocol Data Unit) sessions	int @UEs per UPF
Maximum number of UEs	int @UEs registered in slice
N6Protection	*list of PCC rules

Fig. 5. Program supported instances in network slice lifecycle.

Since mapping is an essential part of the PoC that has been developed, the following subsections provide a pseudo-code representative of the code used in the PoC. It is important to note that the developed PoC is technology-specific and depends on the equipment used, based on a network characterization made in previous work, as seen in [11–14]. Additionally, the following pseudocode uses standardized parameter

names whenever possible, which may have a different performance impact than the equivalent functionality of the used network solution. Therefore, the mapping requires adjustments when using a different 5G network solution.

The code used was Python, and the pseudocode provided considers Python mathematical operators. The variables provided by the user are characterized by a ‘slice.‘parameter name’’, while the other variables are provided to the DT to configure the network. Table 3 extends some of the abbreviations used in the following code.

5.2.1. RAN mapping

The pseudocode in Appendix A.4 gives an overview of how mapping in the PoC is done. The missing configurations use predefined testbed values or are directly mapped from user-provided values. The

Table 3
Glossary.

ARP	Allocation and Retention Priority
PDU	Packet Data Unit
SSC	Session and Service Continuity
AMBR	Aggregate Maximum Bit Rate
MICO	Mobile Initiated Connection Only
DRX	Discontinuous Reception
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
BLER	Block Error Rate

code defines a variety of RAN configurations, including 5QI configurations, protocol configurations (MAC, RLC, and PDCP), scheduling configurations, and DRX configurations.

5.2.2. CN mapping

The pseudocode in [Appendix A.5](#) represents only part of the features and QoS used in the CN mapping. The PoC code also includes the configuration of PCC rules, which is a direct mapping from [Appendix A.1](#) to network parameters, as well as the configuration of user profiles, DNNs, IP Pools, and SNSSAIs. These configurations use specific integer numbers and the slice ID. Since these values are technology-specific or implementation-specific, they are not presented here.

5.2.3. UE mapping

The UE mapping involves using configurations defined in [Appendix A.2](#) directly mapped to UE network settings. Additionally, it is necessary to obtain the following values from the selected network slice to configure the UE network settings: Mission Critical Service, High Latency Communication, MICO, SNSSAI, and DNN.

5.3. Digital twin

The developed DT is a simplified version of the proposed one with limited capabilities. The developed version focuses on providing the necessary functionalities for the slice manager's operation. As the work aims to develop a PoC of a generic network slice manager capable of deploying and managing custom network slices rather than creating a comprehensive digital twin of a specific 5G network. The developed system uses the digital twin layer, but for the PoC, only the interfaces provided by the digital twin are essential. The details of the digital twin's implementation are not critical for the proposed work.

The current version of the DT can convert network functionalities derived from mappings into network configurations. The produced network configurations are enforced on the respective 5G network functions, including RAN, UPF, SMF (Session Management Function), AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function), and UDM (Unified Data Management). The interaction with these different network functions is done through proprietary interfaces.

Additionally, the DT already has monitoring capabilities, documented in [\[46\]](#). The monitoring will be later integrated with the slice manager to provide more functionalities and complete network slice lifecycle management.

6. Solution evaluation

To assess the developed PoC, its capability to provide the primary three services within a 5G network (eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC) was verified. Each evaluated slice focuses on the performance of its respective service type, with significantly different requirements from one another. This approach ensures a more robust evaluation of the developed slice manager. The section begins by introducing the 5GAIner network used for the evaluation, followed by an outline of the configured values for each tested slice. Subsequently, the section presents and discusses how the tests were performed.

Table 4
gNodeB Technical specifications.

Specification	Values
Maximum bandwidth	20 MHz with 30 kHz subcarrier spacing
Frequency band	Center frequency of 3790.02 MHz (n78 band)
Output power per port	24 dBm
Demultiplexing	TDD
DL Modulation	BPSK; QPSK; 16/64/256QAM
UL Modulation	BPSK; QPSK; 16/64QAM
MIMO	4T4R
Slot assignment	Dual-period 7 Downlink: 3 Uplink (Slot structure 102)

6.1. 5GAIner network

5GAIner is a commercial-graded real-world infrastructure supporting some Release 17 (R17) functionalities. This platform is at the core of Portuguese facility infrastructure. This 5G network spans various geographical locations, including the Instituto de Telecomunicações (IT) of Aveiro and the University of Aveiro. Primarily, IT and its partners utilize this infrastructure for research, development, testing, and validation of diverse use cases and 5G technologies. Presently, the network supports eMBB and URLLC slices and encompasses several features facilitating the provision of mMTC slices.

Operating within a reserved band of Altice, a Portuguese operator, the network's antenna configurations used in the evaluations are detailed in [Table 4](#), providing essential insights into the network's performance.

For further details, refer to [\[15\]](#). While the document discusses the network in Release 15, it currently operates with full support for Release 16 and includes some R17 functionalities. However, there have been no significant alterations in the network's baseline performance or hardware. Therefore, the presented results and descriptions remain an accurate network representation.

5GAIner network does not have a simplified method for machine-to-machine communication to directly transmit the commands generated in the Digital Twin (DT). Therefore, the DT uses Selenium to access the network configuration interface of each network function.

6.2. Evaluated network slices

The chosen values for each network slice were not specifically tailored to any specific use case. Instead, they aimed to reflect possible performance characteristics of the respective slice type, considering the constraints specified in [Table 2](#). The selected values for each slice are detailed in [Table 5](#). The significant distinctions in the defined values are intended to enforce different configurations in each slice, showcasing the versatility and robustness of the developed solution. This approach also serves as a valuable test for the slice manager, demonstrating its ability to manage diverse network configurations.

The selected network slices serve distinct primary purposes:

- (1) eMBB focuses on achieving high throughput with relatively high reliability and priority. To achieve this, it employs high throughput and packet size, medium reliability and priority, medium-low latency, high communication frequency, and guaranteed throughput per UE.
- (2) URLLC prioritizes high reliability and low latency, featuring medium-low throughput and packet size, maximum reliability and priority, low latency, medium communication frequency, and assured throughput per UE and slice. The guaranteed and maximum throughput values are much higher than necessary to ensure enough resources for low latency with high reliability.
- (3) mMTC aims at high connection density and low energy consumption, employing low throughput, reliability, priority and communication frequency, medium packet size, and high latency and terminal density. The number of PDU sessions is undefined

Table 5
Network slices evaluated.

Parameter name	eMBB	URLLC	mMTC
Slice identification	eMBB	URLLC	mMTC
Administrative state	UNLOCKED		
Operational state	ENABLED		
Coverage area	IT		
SST	1	2	3
SD	123456		
DNN	eMBB	URLLC	mMTC
Priority label	70	100	10
UE mobility level	Stationary		
Reliability	99.9	99.999	99
Uplink max packet size	2000	150	500
Downlink latency	20	10	500
Uplink latency	20	10	500
Delay tolerance	NOT_SUPPORTED		SUPPORTED
Downlink deterministic communication	SUPPORTED		
Downlink deterministic periodicity	5	10	500
Uplink deterministic communication	SUPPORTED		
Uplink deterministic periodicity	5	10	500
Downlink guaranteed throughput per UE	2100	240	–
Uplink guaranteed throughput per UE	2100	240	–
Downlink maximum throughput per UE	3000	600	–
Uplink maximum throughput per UE	3000	600	–
Downlink guaranteed throughput per slice	–	2000	–
Uplink guaranteed throughput per slice	–	2000	–
Downlink maximum throughput per slice	–	6000	–
Uplink maximum throughput per slice	–	6000	–
Terminal density	5	10	500
Maximum number of PDU sessions	15	20	–
Maximum number of UEs	30	25	10 ⁶
N6Protection	Default rule		

due to the 5GAIner's value limit set at 255. The terminal density refers to the anticipated number of active UEs transmitting per antenna at each moment.

In all evaluated network slices, the N6protection is defined with the default rule, allowing unrestricted communications without throughput limitations. This evaluation primarily focuses on performance rather than restricting end device connectivity or other functionalities configurable via PCC rules. Although it was possible to define guaranteed throughput and maximum throughput in the PCC rules, the RAN's limitation of 20 MHz spectrum constraints its maximum throughput, reaching around 160 Mbps downlink and 40 Mbps uplink-far below the UPF's limitation, which exceeds 1 Gbps in both directions.

6.3. Performed tests

The tests performed are an adaptation of the 3GPP and 5G-ACIA recommendations presented in [47,48]. The adaptations were made to better reflect the focus of our use cases, which have been shaped by different scenarios and verticals while experimenting with and deploying a variety of industrial use cases in the testbed used.

The performance evaluation of each selected slice was conducted under three distinct scenarios:

- (1) Packet size of 1400 bytes with a periodicity of 5 ms. Objective ensure 99.9% reliability by delivering packets with less than 20 ms latency.
- (2) Packet size of 150 bytes with a periodicity of 10 ms. Objective ensure 99.999% reliability by delivering packets with less than 10 ms latency.
- (3) Packet size of 500 bytes with a periodicity of 500 ms. Objective ensure 99% reliability by delivering packets with a maximum latency of 500 ms, supporting 500 active end devices on the same antenna, and reducing UE energy consumption.

Each test was conducted separately, focusing on either uplink transmission or downlink transmission. These evaluations aim to measure the end device energy consumption, latency, and packet loss of 5G communication for each slice in each scenario. Additionally, latency and

packet loss are assessed while other devices utilizing the default eMBB slice are active on the network. By conducting tests in various scenarios, it becomes feasible to demonstrate how each slice's performance aligns with the specified communication criteria.

Even though the network used supports some R17 features, currently, R17 5G end devices are not commercially available. The end devices used only support R15, which impacts the performance obtained since some functionalities enabled are not supported by the UE used. This limitation restricts their performance compared to what has been configured.

The following subsections describe how the tests were performed to measure each of the communication KPIs, detailing the test setup and the methods used to obtain each metric. The tests were divided into Latency and Packet Loss measurements, with UE Throughput also recorded. Energy measurements were conducted separately.

6.3.1. Latency and packet loss measurement

Latency and packet loss measurements are conducted using the UE2 configuration depicted in Fig. 6. Downlink latency is measured by transmitting packets from the server through the 5G network to the UE (Huawei CPE2 pro), which then forwards the packets through an Ethernet connection to a single-board computer connected to the 5G network's outer router, subsequently delivering the packets back to the server. Consequently, uplink latency measurements involve the opposite direction of packet transmission. Latency values are determined by calculating the time difference between the moment a packet is sent from the server and the moment it arrives back at the server. Packet Loss is assessed by counting the number of lost packets during the tests. Each test is performed by sending exactly 30000 packets.

6.3.2. Throughput measurement

To measure throughput, it is used the 5G network traces that provide individual throughput measurements for each end device. The results were taken during the Latency and Packet Loss measurements.

Fig. 6. Network deployment for evaluation.

6.3.3. Energy measurement

The assessment of energy consumption in the 5G network utilizes the UE1 configuration shown in Fig. 6. Here, a Huawei P40 Pro serves as the UE and a USB Digital tester (FNIRSI FNB58) measures the UE's energy consumption. Each test scenario is conducted for one hour.

During energy consumption measurements, the Huawei P40 Pro is set with a fully charged battery, minimum screen brightness, and ultra energy-saving mode activated, using the Termux application to execute necessary commands throughout the entire test duration. All energy consumption data presented excludes any energy expended by the end device under the same configurations but not connected to the network.

6.4. PoC performance evaluation

As previously discussed, the PoC developed consists of several operations, each with a different impact on the overall performance of the system. Therefore, the performance evaluation measures the impact of four specific PoC operations:

- Slice Manager: Composed by the various functions (CSMF, NSMF, and NSSMFs).
- Mapping: Focuses on the part of NSSMF functions that convert slice parameters into standard 5G functionalities.
- DT: Converts standard functionalities to proprietary 5G functionalities and generates the commands to be enforced in the 5GAIner network.
- 5G network configuration: Configures the 5GAIner network using the proprietary API.

To analyze the time of each operation, the different functionalities of the system were executed, introducing probes at each step of the code to obtain the associated timestamps, which were then used to calculate the execution time of each operation. The following functionalities provided by the PoC were evaluated:

- Get all slices: Retrieves all parameters of all slices configured in the CSMF or NSMF.
- Get specific slices: Retrieves all parameters of a specific slice configured in the CSMF or NSMF.
- Create slices: Creates and configures the requested slice on the 5GAIner network.
- Update slices: Updates the parameters of the requested slice.
- Delete slices: Deletes the slice and removes all configurations related to the specific slice from the network.
- Get slice UEs: Retrieves all UEs associated with the slice.
- Add UE: Associates a UE with the slice.
- Remove UE: Disassociates a UE from the slice.
- Dynamic Slicing: Reconfigures the 5GAIner network to disable the old slice and enable the new slice.

7. Network slice manager experimental results

This section presents and discusses the results obtained during the evaluation. It provides an overview of the overall results obtained in the assessment, demonstrating how each slice is adapted to its specific scenario. The section concludes with a demonstration of dynamic slicing provided by the network slice manager.

7.1. Slice performance results

The complete description and discussion of the results can be found in Appendix A.6. Here, the discussion primarily focuses on whether slices fulfill requirements and performance metrics. The performance values of each slice in each scenario are detailed in Table 6. The table includes various requirements and performance metrics for each evaluation:

- UE Energy Consumed: Energy consumed by the UE during the 1-hour test.
- Effective Throughput: Percentage of throughput used in user plane transmission compared to total throughput [(RLC (Radio Link Control) layer throughput)/(MAC (Medium Access Control) layer throughput)].
- Reliability: Percentage of packets that arrive before latency requirements.
- Mean Latency: Average latency of all successfully transmitted packets.

The results of Scenario 1 highlight that the eMBB slice performs optimally when the network experiences no congestion. However, when congestion occurs, the slice lacks sufficient resources, leading to a failure to ensure the reliability of uplink transmission. As expected, the other two slices cannot meet the performance requirements of this scenario. The URLLC slice's throughput limitation results in a high number of packet drops, significantly impacting reliability and latency.

The results of Scenario 2 reveal that the URLLC slice exhibits greater alignment with the scenario's requirements, demonstrating higher reliability across all evaluations. Despite the eMBB slice consuming significantly higher resources, it shows lower reliability. This showcases the critical importance of resource optimization in ensuring performance for use cases with stringent requirements. The network slice manager plays a vital role in adjusting configurations to optimize resources and performance based on requirements. However, the slice manager's capabilities are constrained by the combined performance of the network and the end device. This scenario highlights that even with the configurations tailored to the use case, performance is limited by the capabilities of the network and end device.

The results of Scenario 3 reveal that all slices can support an mMTC use case, achieving reliability levels of 100% or close, exceeding the reliability requirements. However, differences emerge in energy consumption and effective throughput among the slices. While URLLC demonstrates better effective throughput, mMTC exhibits the lowest UE energy consumption, along with a good performance in effective throughput. This scenario demonstrates that even in use cases with less stringent requirements, slice configuration plays a crucial role in differentiating performance in terms of communication resource utilization and end-device energy consumption.

Even though not evaluated in Scenario 3, considering the average uplink throughput of the antenna used, which is 36 Mbps with a 20 MHz bandwidth and 162 Mbps with a 100 MHz bandwidth, and the MAC throughput experienced by the mMTC slice is 317 kbps, as presented in Table 14, each antenna would be able to support 113 UEs for a 20 MHz bandwidth and 511 UEs for a 100 MHz bandwidth. The average downlink values of the same network are 165 Mbps with 20 MHz bandwidth and 960 Mbps with 100 MHz bandwidth, supporting many more UEs than in the uplink. Considering these values, the configurations of the mMTC slice fully support the expected requirements on an antenna with 100 MHz bandwidth.

Table 6
Network slice performance.

Scenario	Requirement and performance metric	Target value	Slice performance				
			eMBB	URLLC	mMTC		
1	DL	UE energy consumed (W/h)	–	0.599	0.590	0.637	
		Effective throughput (%)	–	80.3	79.8	76.7	
	UL	UE energy consumed (W/h)	–	0.842	0.610	0.600	
		Effective throughput (%)	–	65.1	99.1	94.4	
	Free network results						
	DL	Reliability (%)	99.9	99.99	22.61	99.39	
		Mean latency (ms)	<20	3.15	14.04	5.79	
	UL	Reliability (%)	99.9	99.96	0	99.38	
		Mean latency (ms)	<20	6.79	5453.52	8.87	
	Congested network results						
	DL	Reliability (%)	99.9	100	22.02	99.540	
		Mean latency (ms)	<20	3.087	15.53	4.55	
	UL	Reliability (%)	99.9	99.69	0	94.243	
		Mean latency (ms)	<20	7.49	5449.16	10.37	
	2	DL	UE energy consumed (W/h)	–	0.693	0.604	0.603
			Effective throughput (%)	–	63.1	63.2	62.04
		UL	UE energy consumed (W/h)	–	0.615	0.599	0.585
			Effective throughput (%)	–	6.3	15.0	29.3
Free network results							
DL		Reliability (%)	99.999	99.620	99.723	99.530	
		Mean latency (ms)	<10	3.09	3.09	3.20	
UL		Reliability (%)	99.999	99.283	99.413	97.930	
		Mean latency (ms)	<10	4.73	3.86	5.49	
Congested network results							
DL		Reliability (%)	99.999	99.627	99.680	99.567	
		Mean latency (ms)	<10	3.04	3.08	3.38	
UL		Reliability (%)	99.999	95.460	98.583	38.803	
		Mean latency (ms)	<10	4.87	4.61	12.43	
3		DL	UE energy consumed (W/h)	–	0.485	0.485	0.428
			Effective throughput (%)	–	78.1	77.0	75.7
		UL	UE energy consumed (W/h)	–	0.706	0.551	0.465
			Effective throughput (%)	–	1.9	2.9	2.7
	Free network results						
	DL	Reliability (%)	99	100	100	100	
		Mean latency (ms)	<500	3.17	3.23	110.00	
	UL	Reliability (%)	99	100	100	99.8	
		Mean latency (ms)	<500	20.94	20.90	55.16	
	Congested network results						
	DL	Reliability (%)	99	100	100	100	
		Mean latency (ms)	<500	3.12	3.17	109.96	
	UL	Reliability (%)	99	100	100	99.8	
		Mean latency (ms)	<500	20.50	20.96	54.23	

7.2. Slice manager performance evaluation

This section presents the time taken by the PoC to execute each request, broken down by the time spent on each component. Each request was performed ten times, and execution times were consistent across all trials. Therefore, the mean time for each request is presented here.

The complete execution time for the PoC to process each request can be seen in Fig. 7. From the results, it is evident that the time to configure the network significantly impacts PoC performance, as the 5G network configuration time ranges from few to hundreds of seconds, while the Slice Manager and DT processing times are below 500 ms. Due to the extensive time required to configure the network, a specific functionality has been implemented in the PoC for dynamic slicing, wherein both slices need to be already created before UEs transition between slices.

This mechanism for dynamic slicing reduces the number of configurations made in the network to a minimum, resulting in the demonstrated performance, which reduces the time to change the slice from 1

or 2 min to around 3.5 s. During experimentation, it was verified that after the commands are configured on the network, the performance impact on UEs is immediate.

7.3. Dynamic slicing testing

To demonstrate the dynamic slicing functionality provided by the network slice manager, mMTC and eMBB slices were utilized when UE communicated in scenarios 2 and 3. The measurements were performed following the same methodology as previous tests, and the results are shown in Fig. 8. Notably, the energy consumption of the end device in scenario 2 did not exhibit significant differences and thus is not displayed in the figure.

Scenario 2 results are presented in Fig. 8(a). The left graph shows the complete latency results, while the right graph zooms in on the results to the moment a slice is changed. The results include both uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) latency.

Scenario 3 results are shown in Fig. 8(b). The two top graphs present the downlink energy consumption, the two middle graphs illustrate the

Fig. 7. PoC execution time for each request.

uplink energy consumption, and the two bottom graphs present the uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) latency results. As in Scenario 2, all the left graphs of Scenario 3 show the performance results of the entire test, while the right graphs zoom in to the moment a slice is changed.

In scenario 3, slices were changed every three minutes, while in scenario 2, slices were changed approximately every three seconds. From the results, the eMBB slice presents a latency below 10 ms for all packets in scenario 2 and below 50 ms and 20 ms for the uplink and downlink of scenario 3, respectively. The mMTC slice has packets with latency varying from 10 ms to 80 ms in scenario 2 uplink while not presenting much change from the eMBB slice in scenario 2 downlink. In scenario 3, the mMTC slice has uplink latency varying from 20 to 100 ms and a downlink latency ranging from a few milliseconds to more than 300 ms. This change in latency demonstrates the change between both slices during the dynamic slicing evaluation.

The slice change can also be observed in scenario 3's energy consumption, where the eMBB slice consistently has a minimum energy consumption of close to 1 W and a maximum of around 6 W. In contrast, the mMTC slice has a minimum energy consumption of around 0.5 W and a maximum of around 4 W.

For scenario 3, results begin with the eMBB slice for three minutes, followed by three minutes with the mMTC slice, and then switch back to the eMBB slice. In scenario 2, results start with the eMBB slice for around three seconds, then change to the mMTC slice for another three seconds, and then switch back to the eMBB slice.

The images showing results for only 2 or 4 s are used to assess if the slice change affected communication performance. No significant abnormal behaviors were observed, indicating that the slice change does not cause any substantial increase in latency or energy consumption that could affect the KPIs required by use cases. Moreover, the change between slices in the downlink communication of scenario 2, where both slices have similar performance, demonstrates no significant impact on latency. This result shows a sporadic packet with higher latency, which can occur when not using a URLLC slice.

8. Discussion

As mentioned earlier, this work is part of a larger endeavour with the ultimate goal of developing a network slice manager capable of automating the configuration of a 5G network, ensuring it supports the required network slice for end users. The work began with analyzing the different mechanisms and features existing in a 5G network, as discussed in [11–13]. This was followed by mapping the mechanisms and features of a 5G network to the attributes that define a network slice or an industrial use case, as discussed in [14]. The previous work was important to understand how the 5G network works, to finally

design and develop a slice manager capable of configuring the 5G network to support the slices required by the end user, as presented in this document.

The results demonstrate that the developed network slice manager can optimize existing resources to meet required performance but is unable to create resources where they do not exist. The evaluated scenarios illustrate these aspects. In scenario 1, the eMBB network slice fully met its performance requirements when the network was not congested, as expected since it was tailored to this scenario. However, it failed to meet the uplink requirements in a congested network, due to lack of resources.

In scenario 2, the URLLC slice created by the slice manager demonstrated performance close to the requirements but was unreliable in providing the required low latency. In this case, the slices created are limited by the resources and capabilities of the network and the end device, as expected when using an R15 end device. Therefore, the slice manager can only optimize the available resources trying to provide the required performance. In scenario 3, all slices were fully capable of meeting the reliability requirements. However, when analyzing the number of active UEs per antenna, only mMTC and URLLC can support it. Furthermore, considering UE energy consumption, it is evident that the mMTC slice is optimized for the requirements.

The dynamic slicing test also demonstrates the capability of the network slice manager to provide dynamic slicing, showing that the developed manager can adjust the communication performance of all end devices in a slice in real time without requiring transmission disruption or having any significant impact on communication performance.

The results demonstrate the network slice manager can provide the demanded network slices. However, when resources are depleted or the requested performance exceeds equipment capabilities, the performance behavior deviates from the desired outcome. Despite these limitations, the experimented slices maintained priorities as demanded, and performance loss occurred as expected. The slice manager optimized available network resources to accommodate slices demanded by the industrial user. The selected slices, substantially different, demonstrated the expected performance, serving as a robust stress test for the developed network slice manager. This test significantly changed the network load conditions, showcasing the flexibility and capacity of network management. These findings confirm the effectiveness of the proposed design for a network slice manager in deploying and managing network slices within a 5G network.

The results validate the four key contributions of the developed network slice manager PoC. (1) It offers network slices customized for the three primary 5G services, tailored to the demanded requirements. (2) The constructed slices within each service type are completely customized. (3) Despite the network slice manager not being carrier-graded, the configured slices maintain the infrastructure TRL, ensuring

Fig. 8. Results of dynamic slicing evaluation.

carrier-graded slices that represent a future commercial solution using the current 5G release. (4) The slice manager provides mechanisms for dynamic network slicing, enabling real-time changes in slice communication performance without disruption or significant impact on communication.

While the document tested only three network slices, the network slice manager can support numerous other configurations. Due to the vast number of possibilities, it is impractical to test and present every configuration in a single document. Nevertheless, the network slice manager presented here has been used in different practical use cases, such as [45], where we analyzed an industrial with two different network slices deployed in the 5GAIner network. This is one of multiple examples where our solution configures the network to support multiple network slices.

This document also evaluated the performance of the PoC developed and demonstrated that the Slice Manager and DT systems execute

requests quickly. However, the 5G network configuration time significantly degrades the PoC performance due to the proprietary API's performance and the time the infrastructure takes to adapt to the requested changes. This API is the only one available to configure the testbed used, which is the main limitation of PoC's performance improvement.

The testbed used is based on a commercial SA 5G network, designed to be almost static to ensure the reliability and resilience required by network operators. This design limits the network's reconfigurability, significantly increasing the time it takes for each configuration to become effective. This limitation is evident in the execution of dynamic slicing mechanisms in the PoC, where the slice manager sends a single command to one network function, yet the network takes more than three seconds to implement it. Full reconfiguration of a slice requires dozens of commands to multiple network functions, making real-time dynamic slicing impossible in the current setup. However, future releases of 5G systems are expected to evolve in order to achieve complete dynamic slicing.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

André Perdigão: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **José Quevedo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Rui L. Aguiar:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

A.1. N6protection parameters

Each item in the list consists of the values outlined in Table 7. The variable type is intended to define the type of N6protection, specifically set as "PCC Rule" to designate a PCC rule, while the other variables encompass the configurations for the PCC rule.

A.2. End-device parameters

The parameters configured for the end-device manager are detailed in Table 8.

A.3. Mapping network configurations

The relevant network configurations in each of the mappings are presented in three distinct tables: RAN configurations in Table 9, CN configurations in Table 10, and UE configurations in Table 11.

Table 7

N6protection filter parameters.

N6protection parameter name	Expected value
Type	str (PCC Rule)
PCC rule name	str PCC rule name (not allowed [;=""])
PCC rule priority	int (1-4294967295) lower value higher priority
Destination IP network	any IPv4 network
Mask length of destination IP network	int (0-32)
Start of covered Layer 4 ports	int (0-65535)
End of covered Layer 4 ports	int (0-65535 \geq startport)
Uplink guaranteed bit rate in UPF	int (0-20000000) kbit/s
Downlink guaranteed bit rate in UPF	int (0-20000000) kbit/s
Uplink maximum bit rate in UPF	int (0-20000000) kbit/s
Downlink maximum bit rate in UPF	int (0-20000000) kbit/s
Layer 4 Protocol	str (ANY - GRE - ICMP - TCP - UDP)
PassBlock	str (pcc_action_pass-pcc_action_block-ue_initiated-server_initiated) this value is network specific

Table 8

End-device manager parameters.

End device manager parameter Name	Expected value
IMSI	int Identifies the first International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) to associate with a slice.
number of IMSIs	int Defines the number of consecutive IMSIs to associate.
UE Access Management Data	boolean Defines if the slice will define UE AMDATA, if the UE has access to multiple slices, only one can define the AMDATA.
Default slice of DNN	str (TRUE-FALSE) If UE has access to multiple slices with the same DNN and different SNSSAIs, only one SNSSAI can be the default. This is the one used if UE while attaching, does not select the SNSSAI.
If AMDATA=TRUE	
UE can send SNSSAI when attaching	str (TRUE-FALSE) Defines if UE can send the SNSSAI when attaching.
Aggregate maximum bit rate uplink	int kbit/s
Aggregate maximum bit rate downlink	int kbit/s
If numIMSIs = 1 and AMDATA=TRUE	
UE IPv4	str Any IPv4 inside the IPpool of the selected slice.
UE IPv6	str any IPv6

A.4. RAN pseudocode

Listing 1 gives an overview of how RAN mapping is performed in the PoC.

Listing 1: RAN mapping

```

Scheduling Type = Basic
If latency requirements are lower than 20 ms:
    Scheduling type = Low Latency
    PDCP DL out of Order = True if slice.DL Latency lower than 10 ms
    PDCP UL Out of Order = True if slice.UL Latency lower than 10 ms
    If latency requirements are lower than 5 ms:
        Transmission mode = Unacknowledged Mode

DL reordering timer = slice.DL Latency
DL Maximum HARQ retransmissions = slice.DL Latency // 20
RLC DL Reassembly time = slice.DL Latency
UL reordering timer = slice.UL Latency
UL Maximum HARQ retransmissions = slice.UL Latency // 20
RLC UL Reassembly time = slice.UL Latency

service type = URLLC if slice.SST equals 2; = eMBB if slice.SST equals 1 and UE guaranteed throughput higher than 1 Mbps; else = Normal

If Latency requirements lower than 20 ms:
    Scheduling Option = Configured Grant
    if slice.UL Deterministic Communication is Supported:
        if slice.UL Deterministic Periodicity higher than 250 ms:

```

```

Scheduling option = Scheduling Request
Scheduling Request Period = slice.UL Latency / 2
if slice.Reliability higher than 99.99%:
    Scheduling Request Period = slice.UL Latency / 4
if slice.UL Latency lower equal to 5 ms:
    //Default configuration
else:
    Configured Grant Interval = slice.UL Deterministic Periodicity
    if slice.Reliability higher than 99.99%:
        Configured Grant Interval = slice.UL Deterministic Periodicity/2
    if slice.UL Latency lower than 10:
        Configured Grant Interval = slice.UL Deterministic Periodicity/4
    Configured Grant Duration = 3 * slice.UL Deterministic Periodicity
    Configured Grant Data Volume = slice.UL Maximum Packet Size
else:
    Scheduling Option = Scheduling Request
    Scheduling Request Period = slice.UL Latency

Enable UL and DL IBLER scheduling mechanisms
if slice.reliability higher than 99.99%:
    Enable UL Slot Aggregation
    Limit UL Max Modulation Coding Scheme to 23
    Scheduling type = High Reliability
    Service type = URLLC
    Double Configured Grant Data Volume
    If latency requirements are lower than 20 ms:

```

Table 9
RAN mapping network configurations.

Network configuration standard name	Configuration impact
5QI	5QI is a scalar used as a reference for 5G QoS characteristics; this parameter is associated with several communication parameters. In 5G networks, several standard 5QIs have predefined values for multiple QoS parameters that are pre-configured in the AN.
QCI	This configuration were predominantly used in 4G networks for RAN performance identification, this network solution also employs it in 5G.
Transmission mode	It designates whether the communication occurs in Acknowledge Mode (AM) or Unacknowledged Mode (UM). Only in AM, the RAN verify if the packet is successfully transmitted.
ID of CELL	This parameter serves to identify the RAN cell and is analogous to the RAN RU (Radio Unit).
Network areas	The RAN network comprises distinct zones, and this parameter identifies the specific area, analogous to the identification of a RAN CU/DU (Centralized Unit/Distributed Unit), this RAN solution does not differentiate between CU and DU.
Average window	Specifies the duration utilized by the RAN network for calculating guaranteed and maximum bit rates.
Packet Delay Budget (PDB)	Specifies the expected packet delay in RAN transmission.
Discard timer	Specify the maximum duration for RAN transmission in AM mode before discarding a packet due to transmission failure.
Reordering timer	Determine the maximum time that the PDCP (Packet Data Convergence Protocol) layer waits to reorder packets in case of packet subdivision during RAN transmission.
PDCP Out Of Order Delivery	Defines whether packets can be transmitted to UE or CN out of sequence, allowing subsequent packets to proceed even if a packet is lost during transmission, or if all subsequent packets must wait for the missed packet to maintain order.
PDCP Duplication	Specifies whether RAN transmission duplicates packets to enhance transmission reliability.
DRX parameters	Specifies various DRX (Discontinuous Reception) parameters.
Idle/Inactive Timer	Defines the duration from the last transmission from/to the UE until a change to RRC_INACTIVE or RRC_IDLE state occurs.
Guaranteed bit rate	Specifies the guaranteed downlink and uplink rates for RAN transmission.
MAC scheduling priority	Specifies the scheduling priority in the MAC layer compared to other communications.
RLC reassembly	Determines the maximum duration that RAN waits before reassembling packets in the RLC layer.
Transmission IBLER	If IBLER is selected in SchOption (Scheduling Option), it defines the target IBLER for transmission.
Configured grant interval	If preallocation is enabled in SchOption, it determines the interval between resource pre-allocated transmission resources.
Configured grant data volume	If preallocation is enabled in SchOption, it specifies the amount of Data that can be transmitted in each pre-allocated slot.
Maximum HARQ Retransmissions	Determines the maximum number of packet retransmissions before discarding.
PDCCH BLER	Specifies the target BLER in the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH).
Scheduling request period	If SRperiod is enabled in SchOption, it specifies the interval between each uplink transmission request.
Configured grant duration	If smart preallocation is enabled in SchOption, it determines the maximum duration for reserving preallocated resources after the last uplink or downlink transmission.
Slot aggregation	Defines whether UL transmission utilizes slot aggregation.
SST	Specifies the Slice/Service Type (SST) of the slice used.
SD	Specifies the Slice Descriptor (SD) of the slice used.
Cell Max number of UEs	Determines the maximum number of UEs that can be attached to the same RAN DU.
Network slice RAN resource allocation	Defines the minimum, maximum and average resource allocation of RAN to the network slice.

Table 10
CN mapping network configurations.

Network configuration standard name	Configuration impact
UPF name	Contains UPF(s) identification.
DNN, APN	Data Network Name/Access Point Name used by slice.
5QI	5G QoS Identifier
Slice-MBR	Slice maximum bit rate.
ARP priority	Defines ARP (Allocation and Retention Priority) priority.
PDU session type	Define the primary type of the PDU (Protocol Data Unit) session.
SSC Mode	Specifies the primary Session and Service Continuity (SSC) used.
LADN	Determines whether DNN indicates the Local Area Data Network (LADN).
LBO (Local Breakout)	Defines whether roaming gateways are permitted to use roaming in roaming scenarios.
UP integrity protection	Specifies UP (User Plane) Integrity protection policy.
UP confidentiality protection	Specifies UP confidentiality protection policy.
Preemption capability	Specifies whether the slice can utilize resources allocated to other slices.
Preemption vulnerability	Determines if the slice's network resources can be accessed by other slices.
Maximum number of PDU sessions	Defines the maximum number of PDU sessions allowed to be online simultaneously within the same slice.
Maximum number of UEs	Define the maximum number of UEs associated with a slice.
PCC rules	Contains the information of all PCC Rules of slice.
SD	Slice Descriptor
SST	Slice/Service Type

Table 11
UE mapping network configurations.

Network configuration standard name	Configuration impact
IMSI	Contains the International mobile subscriber identity (IMSI) of the end device.
IP version 4	Define UE static IPv4.
IP version 6	Define UE static IPv6.
AMBR	Define the maximum uplink/downlink throughput that UE can simultaneously send/receive across all slices.
SNSSAI	Slice SNSSAI (Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information).
DNN	Slice DNN (Data Network Name).
MPS (Multimedia Priority Service)	Specifies the provision of MPS (Multimedia Priority Services).
MCS (Mission Critical Service)	Specifies the provision of MCS (Mission Critical Services).
High latency communication	Specifies the provision of High Latency Communication services.
MICO	Determines whether MICO (Mobile Initiated Connection Only) is enabled.

```

Enable PDCP Duplication
Service Type = URLLC
Calculate Transmission IBLER based on slice.Reliability
if slice.reliability higher than 99.9%:
    PDCCH BLER = Transmission IBLER

Packet Delay Budget = minimum of slice.UL Latency and
    slice.DL Latency
UL Discard Timer = slice.UL Latency
DL Discard Timer = slice.DL Latency
if slice.Delay Tolerance is supported:
    DRX long_cycle = 5 * slice.DL Latency
    DRX short_cycle = slice.DL Latency
    DRX short_timer = 5
    Inactive Timer = slice.DL Latency * 100 // 1000 + 1
    reordering Timer = maximum value
    Discard Timer = None
    RLC Reassembly Timer = maximum value
    Scheduling Option = Scheduling Request
    Scheduling Request Period = Maximum value
    Transmission Mode = Acknowledge Mode
else if slice.DL Latency higher than 30:
    DRX long_cycle = slice.DL Latency

MAC Scheduling Priority = 10 * slice.Priority Label
Logical Channel Prioritization Restrictions = 1 + ( 106 -
    slice.Priority Label ) * 15 // 100
Priority Level = 1+ ( 100 - slice.Priority Label ) * 126 //
    100

Calculate the Slice resource allocation percentage based
    on available antenna resources and slice resources
    requested
DL Guaranteed Bit Rate = slice.DL Guaranteed Throughput
    per UE
UL Guaranteed Bit Rate = slice.UL Guaranteed Throughput
    per UE

```

A.5. CN pseudocode

Listing 2 gives an overview of how CN mapping is performed in the PoC.

Listing 2: CN mapping

```

ARP priority = 1+(107-slice.Priority Label)*14//100
User Priority = 65534-640*Priority Label
Mission Critical Service = True if slice.Priority Label
    equals 100

PDU Type = slice.PDUType[0]
Allowed PDU Type = slice.PDUType[1:]

SSC Mode = SSC_Mode_1
if slice.UEmobilityLevel is not stationary

```

```

if slice.reliability lower than 99 and UE requires
    guaranteed throughput:
    Allowed SSC Mode = SSC_Mode_3
else if slice.reliability lower than 99:
    Allowed SSC Mode = SSC_Mode_2
else:
    Allowed SSC Mode = SSC_Mode_3
else:
    Allowed SSC Mode = SSC_Mode_2

```

```

UL slice AMBR = slice.UL maximum Throughput per UE
DL slice AMBR = slice.DL maximum Throughput per UE

```

```

Enable high-latency communication and MICO if slice.Delay
    tolerance is Supported

```

A.6. Experimental results

This section presents the results obtained in the performance evaluation of each slice in the three different scenarios. The results obtained in each scenario are presented next.

A.6.1. Scenario 1

This scenario evaluates the performance of each slice when a UE sends a packet of 1400 bytes every 5 ms. The throughput and packet loss obtained by each slice are presented in Table 12. As expected, the URLLC slice, with its limitation in throughput per UE, restricts the throughput to around 600 kbps, making it unsuitable to support this scenario. The other two slices, as seen in terms of throughput and packet loss, show minimal difference in their ability to support the scenario on these KPIs.

The communication latency and end device energy consumption in this scenario are depicted in Fig. 9. As expected, the URLLC slice cannot ensure latency due to congestion and packet drops. The mMTC slice shows lower energy consumption in uplink communications but fails to ensure packet latency for 99.9% of the packets. Meanwhile, the eMBB slice only fails to ensure the 20 ms latency for 99.9% of the packets in uplink communication with other UEs creating noise in the antenna, but it achieves a percentage close to the desired. The higher energy consumption in the eMBB slice is caused by the increased control information exchanged with the network, resulting in higher uplink MAC layer throughput, as shown in Table 12.

A.6.2. Scenario 2

This scenario evaluates the performance of each slice when a UE sends a packet with 150 bytes every 10 ms. From Table 13, it can be observed that all slices exhibit similar throughput in terms of the RLC layer and the downlink of the MAC layer. However, each slice demonstrates a significantly different throughput in terms of uplink in the MAC layer. This discrepancy is caused by the uplink configured grants for communication in the eMBB and URLLC slices. The eMBB slice is expected to handle 1400-byte packets every 5 ms, resulting in close to 2 Mbps in MAC layer uplink throughput, similar to the

Table 12
Scenario 1 throughput and packet loss results with different slices.

Network slice	RLC throughput (kbps)		MAC throughput (kbps)		Packet loss (%)			
	Downlink	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink	Without noise		With noise	
					Downlink	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink
eMBB	2196.621 ± 4.734	2194.822 ± 11.339	2733.859 ± 80.043	3369.067 ± 701.887	0.003	0	0	0.13
URLLC	617.017 ± 33.406	600.310 ± 5.620	773.203 ± 49.579	605.453 ± 73.645	71.89	72.59	71.88	72.59
mMTC	2195.339 ± 5.346	2195.410 ± 8.158	2860.915 ± 64.081	2325.176 ± 376.783	0.170	0	0	0

Fig. 9. Scenario 1 results with the different slices.

Table 13
Scenario 2 throughput and packet loss results with different slices.

Network slice	RLC throughput (kbps)		MAC throughput (kbps)		Packet loss (%)			
	Downlink	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink	Without noise		With noise	
					Downlink	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink
eMBB	141.576 ± 0.605	141.774 ± 0.814	224.028 ± 3.657	2233.840 ± 191.836	0	0	0	0
URLLC	141.610 ± 0.582	141.898 ± 0.758	223.825 ± 2.733	943.134 ± 27.133	0	0	0	0
mMTC	141.572 ± 0.608	141.782 ± 0.737	228.202 ± 2.843	482.320 ± 166.273	0	0	0	0

throughput observed in scenario 1. Conversely, URLLC requires more than twice the uplink throughput for low latency with higher reliability, leading to much higher throughput in the uplink of the MAC layer.

In Fig. 10, the latency and UE energy consumption obtained in this scenario are presented. In the downlink, all slices exhibit similar latency performance, with URLLC showing the best performance in terms of downlink latency and energy consumption. In the uplink communication, the mMTC slice also has the best performance. The performance of the mMTC slice aligns with expectations, as it is not tailored for this scenario. However, URLLC performs worse than required, attributed to the UE's having R15 software, which does not support URLLC configurations introduced in R16 onwards, essential for this scenario.

A.6.3. Scenario 3

This scenario evaluates the performance of slices when UE sends a packet with 500 bytes each 500 ms. Table 14 presents throughput and reliability. As expected, in this scenario there is no packet drop, and the eMBB slice exhibits higher MAC layer throughput.

In the results presented in Fig. 11, there is a noticeable difference, with the mMTC slice exhibiting much higher latency compared to the other slices. However, since latency is not critical in this scenario, the results are acceptable. The increase in latency is attributed to features aimed at reducing energy consumption and increasing connection density. As observed, the mMTC slice consumes less energy most of the time compared to the other slices. It is worth noting that some packets in the downlink arrived after the 500 ms mark, partly due to the supported delay tolerance. In this case, the network slice manager was configured to provide less strict configurations in an attempt to reduce energy consumption, despite the potential for some packets arriving after the required latency.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

(a) Latency Results

(b) Energy Results

Fig. 10. Scenario 2 results with different slices.

Table 14

Scenario 3 throughput and packet loss results with different slices.

Network slice	RLC throughput (kbps)		MAC throughput (kbps)		Packet loss (%)			
	Downlink	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink	Without noise		With noise	
					Downlink	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink
eMBB	8.484 ± 0.224	8.684 ± 0.570	10.856 ± 1.103	438.935 ± 84.118	0	0	0	0
URLLC	8.484 ± 0.224	8.688 ± 0.506	11.007 ± 1.064	291.151 ± 56.701	0	0	0	0
mMTC	8.484 ± 1.720	8.692 ± 1.302	11.194 ± 2.506	317.979 ± 37.896	0	0	0	0

(a) Latency Results

(b) Energy Results

Fig. 11. Scenario 3 results with different slices.

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